

INDIAN OCEAN
COMMISSION

The Case for a Regional Maritime Service

Facts and Figures

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1. Executive Summary

This report makes the case for the setting up of a Regional Maritime Service which will act as a vector of regional integration, adapted to the development needs of the region. It presents facts and figures to support the Indian Ocean Commission's (IOC) initiative for the setting up of a viable and sustainable Regional Maritime Service. It is expected that this study helps to get the Member States more involved and take a leadership role in the pursuit of the project.

This proposal emerges from the member States following a long process of exchanges, workshops, meetings, discussions and decisions on maritime transport in the Indian Ocean region. A feasibility study undertaken in 2009 confirmed the need for the setting up of a Regional Maritime Service, albeit operating on a financial deficit in the first few years. However, this deficit does not take into consideration the current and future potential trade with the Eastern and Southern African countries and the wider economic benefits that can be accrued to the region. Furthermore, the proposed Regional Maritime Service will allow the emergence of new opportunities for increased trade in the region; which then can help to make it financially sustainable in the medium to long term.

The proposed Regional Maritime Service will help to:

- create an economic area and infrastructures to attract investors, traders, manufacturers and carriers;
- encourage the production and development of movements of goods and people to achieve a sustainable and inclusive regional development;
- contribute to improve the links to regional markets which are of strong commercial interest, particularly in the Eastern Southern Africa and Indian Ocean region (ESA-IO).

The high level of economic growth in the sub-Saharan Africa region presents potential for increased demand for transport in the ESA-IO region. The opportunities for increased maritime regional trade underline the need for a long term investment to harness the global potential for development, especially if the region wants to act as a transit between Asian emerging economies and Africa.

One sector having great potential for economic growth and trade in the region is agriculture. This is why the IOC's regional development strategy has identified as one of its priorities the promotion of Madagascar as a potential food granary for the region. Madagascar can supply more than the rice, grains, maize and onion requirements of the region. This objective however cannot be reached with the current maritime services.

The Regional Maritime Service should complement the services provided by the member States and the global carriers operating in the region, in order to optimize the efficiency of the intra-regional and inter-regional maritime services. This should allow gains in autonomy in relation to the "global carriers", local economic development of the region, less dependence on the countries of the North, promote security; especially food security.

The IOC has already set up a Regional Monitoring Committee (RMC) to oversee the process for the setting up of a new Regional Maritime Service. The RMC met in March 2013 for the first time to review progress on the project.

Three of the Member States; Comoros, Mauritius and Seychelles have officially informed the IOC General Secretariat their commitment to the project. There is therefore sufficient willingness on the part of the Member States for the project. However, a more active role of the Member States is now expected. The General Secretariat will call for the 2nd meeting of the RMC early next year. This can be the opportunity to consult on the way forward and to

discuss on how to get Member States take the lead in this project, given that the role of the IOC can only be restricted to one of facilitation and coordination.

Future prospects in maritime transport development seem to be optimistic. COSCO, the largest Chinese maritime operator expressed interest in the IOC project and in 2013 several meetings were held with the IOC.

The IOC's role is defined in the above context. The recommendations of this report include:

1. The IOC should continue to contribute to the improvement of connectivity of regional markets, facilitating trade, the movement of people, and the promotion of inclusive and equitable growth.
2. The IOC should facilitate the development of the Regional Maritime Service to set up a viable and sustainable regional maritime system with modern infrastructure, services, a regional shipping line and agreements on cabotage.
3. An IOC Regional Export to Africa Strategy needs to be formulated.
4. A more active role of the Member States is to be demonstrated. The 2nd meeting of the RMC early next year should be the opportunity for Member States to consult each other on the way forward and agree on how to take the lead in this project.
5. The Government of Mauritius has shown the way to stimulate and accelerate the process. The subsidy mechanism developed by Mauritius for stimulating trade in Africa can be the basis for elaborating a regional mechanism.
6. Discussions should continue with COSCO to further engage it in the project. Dialogue should remain open to any other interested party as well. Dialogue with other companies in the region should be encouraged as well.
7. There is a need to strengthen cooperation among customs and concerned departments on economic and trade data in the Indianoceanie so as to significantly improve policy development on intra and inter-regional trade.
8. The development of the Regional Maritime Service should proceed in parallel with the formulation of the Regional Food Security Programme as the successes of both depend on each other.

2. IOC Policy

The aim of the IOC through this project is to create an economic area with 21st century infrastructure to attract traders, manufacturers and carriers, as an important step towards regional economic integration of the Indianoceanic region.

The proposal is to develop a project to set up a viable and sustainable regional maritime system with modern infrastructure, services, a regional shipping line and agreements on cabotage. By this means the IOC will contribute to the improvement of connectivity of regional markets, facilitating trade, the movement of people, and the promotion of inclusive and equitable growth. The project is the culmination of a long process of diverse exchanges, workshops, meetings, discussion and decisions in terms of maritime transport in the Indianoceanic. This maritime policy builds on previous development work, by consultants and meetings of main stakeholders, covering issues of volumes of trade between IOC and ESA countries, marine transport capacity, costs of transport, infrastructure requirements, legal provisions, technical planning and resource mobilisation. A brief on the whole process is provided below:

- The IOC Symposium 2008 on the theme "globalization and regional integration: the future of the IOC" had recommended the IOC countries to define a regional strategy for maritime transport, and already proposed the establishment of a regional cabotage system;
- Based on the conclusions of the Symposium, a study funded by AFD (French Development Agency) was undertaken in 2009 and concluded on the need for the establishment of regional cabotage system in addition to improve the efficiency of the transport chain, investments in infrastructure and the logistics of the maritime corridor. The implementation of such regional cabotage system would involve the transfer from large ports to smaller ports by shortening the length of road/rail transport to the final destination within the country. Nevertheless, the study concludes that it will be profitable in the medium and long term.
- A COMESA project implemented in 2009/2010 supported the development of a strategy on Transport and Communication and a Plan for priority investment, covering the geographic area of the four regional organizations of the Eastern and Southern Africa – Indian Ocean (ESA-IO) countries. This project which aimed at preparing a Priority Investment Plan included the establishment of a regional shipping company as a priority.
- An IOC flagship study was commissioned by the African Development Bank (AfDB) in 2011, in the context of a shared objective to formalize and expand their partnership on a more strategic basis. This study proposed the development of a regional infrastructure network for multimodal connectivity of the Islands (aviation, maritime, telecommunications) which is crucial for the success of regional integration. A dissemination workshop was organized jointly by the IOC and the AfDB with the support of the expert team on the 17th and 18th of November 2011 in Mauritius. The World Bank, the AFD and the EU were also invited to participate in addition to representatives of the member States. The workshop validated the conclusions and recommendations of the report.
- A regional Conference on the South-western Indian Ocean commercial Corridor on the 15th and 16th of November 2011 in Port-Louis concluded on the need to explore the establishment of a regional shipping company.

- A regional Conference on the supply chain of maritime transport in the Indian Ocean was held during 15th to 19th of October 2012, in Mauritius. This Conference endorsed the conclusions and recommendations for the setting up of a Regional Maritime Service in line with the stakeholders' workshop on maritime transport held in September 11th and 12th 2012.
- A study on the preparation of a strategic development Plan of the IOC undertaken in 2012 maintains the issue of regional connectivity and maritime transport as one of its priorities.
- Maritime transport has been the subject of several working sessions at the economic forums of the Indian Ocean's islands, organized by the Union of Chambers of Commerce and Industry of the Indian Ocean (UCCIIOI) on a yearly basis.
- The main purpose of the partnership Convention signed with the Association of Ports and Islands of the Indian Ocean (APIOI) is the development and strengthening of maritime trade between the islands of the Indian Ocean.
- The first meeting the monitoring committee for the setting up of a regional maritime cabotage system was held in Mauritius on March 14th 2013, in Mauritius, in response to the mandate of the 28th Council of the IOC.
- The last meeting of senior officials of the IOC, first authority of decision of the IOC, having met in October 2012, taking good note of the conclusions and recommendations of the workshop of the main stakeholders held on the 11th and 12th of September 2012, asked the General Secretariat to proceed with the preparation of the establishment's feasibility of a regional cabotage system.
- Council of Ministers of the IOC's decision:
 - The 28th Council of the IOC, on January 17th 2013, in Seychelles, agreed in principle on the setting up of a regional maritime cabotage system and asked the Secretary General to establish a monitoring committee.
 - The 27th Council requested the General Secretariat to follow through the implementation of Aid for Trade Strategy, including the maritime corridor.
 - The 26th Council requested the General Secretariat to follow the recommendations of the « Study on regional maritime servicing within the IOC » financed by French Development Agency (AFD) and to refocus the issue of maritime transport in the 10th EDF framework, particularly towards a *regional maritime Corridor's* project.
 - The 25th Council adopted the Aid for Trade IOC strategy which one of the pillars relates to maritime transport.
 - The 24th Council adopted the set of recommendations on maritime transport of the Symposium « Globalization and regional integration, IOC's future » in March 2008 and concluded on the need to establish a regional shipping company.

3. The Regional Maritime Service: issues and objectives

The present maritime operators of the area do not meet the expectations of the members of the IOC and do not allow local economies to grow as they should. The strategies of the different maritime operators do not correspond to those of the Member States of the IOC and in any case do not fall within the timeframe regional actors may wish. Manufacturers and traders can only see their dependence on these 'global carriers', and have little, or no, ability to negotiate rates. Transport represents 30-40% of the cost of consumer products without the possibility of intervention of the States and even less for the consumers.

The regional transportation system results in costly delays due to inadequate infrastructure, lack of links between national transportation, maintenance difficulties of existing infrastructure and of the incompatibility of the systems of transport between them. Consequently, the region must face the challenge of optimization and modernization of transport infrastructure, with the aim of improving the production and distribution of goods and services.

The Project is designed to overcome the vulnerability of the IOC member states to the threat of globalisation of trade. For they are unable to participate in the global process with the present poor infrastructure facilities they have and the lack of a co-ordinated regional policy. Further regional economic integration and participation in the global economy is limited by the high cost of shipping, the lack of regularity, the dependency on few shipping companies, the poor quality of port infrastructures and the lack of a regional strategy for maritime services.

The Project will open up the region to international shipping lines, reduce shipping costs and provide economies of scale for trade. To respond to these economic and commercial opportunities, the region has to improve its trade facilities and services, including container facilities, freight airline services, security for cargoes and efficient and safe customs facilities. It is also important for the region to establish a wider range of trade partners.

With growth in trade across Africa as a whole, the region needs to be alert and responsive to the emerging opportunities within the wider African region and beyond with other emerging economies. For this it needs a comprehensive, modern, efficient and reliable system of trade transport and connectivity. The member five states of the IOC, and the neighbouring coastal countries of Southern and Eastern continental Africa, which are members of the Tripartite (COMESA-EAC-SADC), have considerable potential for developing regional and international transportation.

Over the next thirty years Sub-Saharan is projected to have an annual growth rate of six per cent and to increase its population size to almost 2 billion. This will have a major impact on the transport demand for Eastern and Southern countries of Africa that border the region of the South West Indian Ocean region. The Indianoceanic region needs a regional strategy on maritime transport to keep pace with these developments on the African continent itself, to avoid being marginalized in the regional trade and to realise its potential as gateway into Africa.

Providing facilities and services to attract international shipping lines is expected to reduce freight rates for shippers. This in turn will promote coastal shipping, transshipment in the region ports and will lead to diverse and more competitive maritime transport services and at the same time expands the East African Coast Countries and Madagascar's feeder port network.

Furthermore, this will encourage traders from Madagascar and the Eastern and Southern Africa (ESA) region which borders the south western Indian Ocean region, to make greater use of maritime transport, especially for the transport of food and household goods producing economies of scale and lower transport unit costs. The Project provides potential for countries of the region to diversify their economies, increase their export base, develop their infrastructures, and increase their underexploited intra-regional trade. In short, it will promote sustainable economic growth focussed on inclusive development.

Sustainable development of the maritime transport sector will provide increased employment and increase technical skills and experience.

4. Technical analysis

The IOC study in 2009 undertaken by Maritime Logistics and Trade Consulting on maritime access in the Indian Ocean concluded on the need for the establishment of regional maritime system with improved efficiency of the transport chain, investments in infrastructure and the logistics of the maritime corridor.

Currently there are seven shipping lines serving the region. The frequency and type of services provided by the shipping lines operating within the region are as follows:

Shipping line/service	Frequency	Ship Size TEUs	Route
Maersk-Safmarine safari service	Weekly	5,000-6,500	Pelapas-Port Louis-Toamasina, Maputo, Pelapas
IOI service	Weekly	3,500	Salalah-Port Victoria-Réunion-Port Louis-Toamasina-Salalah
MSC Cheetah service	Weekly	8,000-9,000	Durban-Port Elizabeth-Port Louis-Singapore-Hong Kong
North Europe-Aust	Weekly	4,000-6,000	Relay transhipment between S A and Australia, New Zealand, linking Cheetah service, and North Europe
CMA-CGM/Delmas	Weekly	1,500-2,200	Djibouti-Port Victoria-Port Louis-Réunion-Durban-Djibouti
MOL-MZK service	Weekly	1,800-2500	Singapore-Port Louis-Réunion-Durban-Maputo-Ngqura-Singapore
PIL-EA2 service	Weekly	1,200-1800	Hong-Kong-Guangzhou-Singapore-Port Louis-Mombassa-Singapore-Hong-Kong
Mitsui Indian Ocean Express service, UAFL/Evergreen
Island loop service	Fortnightly	650	Port-Louis- Réunion-Longoni-Madagascar ports- Port-Louis
Madagascar Express service	Monthly	700	Durban-Tuléar-Toamasina-Port Louis-Réunion-Exhala-Durban
Mauritius Shipping Coraline service	5 trips per month	80-165	Port Louis-Port Mathurin-Agalega-Réunion-Toamasina-Port Louis

Source: UNCTAD Publication 2012

It is evident that the potential for the region could be greatly developed especially in providing better links with Port Victoria- Seychelles and Longoni- Mayotte.

From a series of studies and workshops the following recommendations were made:

- The IOC Symposium 2008 on the theme "globalization and regional integration: recommended the IOC countries define a regional strategy for maritime transport,
- The 2009 IOC study funded the French Development Agency (AFD) concluded that a regional maritime service would be profitable in the medium and long term with an Indian Ocean maritime servicing company covering the principal ports of Mauritius, La Réunion, Madagascar, Mayotte, Comoros, and Seychelles.
- The same study recommended pursuit of a maritime service with two large line routes and one small. The two large lines would operate (1) between Europe and La Réunion, and (2) between the Far East, Africa and Mauritius; the small line would operate between Mauritius, Comoros and Seychelles.

The supply side of the shipping industry has continued to expand despite the economic and financial crisis of 2008.

Larger carriers are restricted to high volume routes connecting the world busiest ports whilst smaller ships can enter almost any port. The introduction of larger ships of 11000+ TEUs on the main East – West routes is leading to the redeployment of ships of 8000+ TEUs to shorter route such as Asia – South Africa. MSC is already using ship of this size on its Cheetah Service calling at Durban, Port Elizabeth Singapore, Mauritius and Hong Kong.

The IOC study undertaken by Maritime Logistics and Trade Consulting has identified two types of container vessel best suited for the region:

1. **BIRK** Container/Cellular of capacity TEUs 500 with Loa 132Mts and Draft 7.20m. The container vessel type Birk will be deployed on the routes Port Louis-Port Reunion-Victoria-Moroni-Port Louis.
2. **PEAR RIVER** Container/Cellular vessel of a higher capacity TEUs 900 with Load 148Mts and draught 8.50m will be deployed on the routes Port Louis-Port Reunion-Longoni-Tomasina-Port Louis

The study did not take into consideration the potential of other linkages in East Africa and in the Indian Ocean region, West and East Coast of Madagascar through ports Tuléar, Majunga, Diego Suarez, Nosy-Bé and Eloha.

The potential linkages involving West Africa and the Eastern Coast of South America need also to be considered with the introduction of larger vessels 9000 + TEUs.

The Project concept proposes the use and further development of one regional transshipment port for the Western Indian Ocean that will also be able to handle larger ships (8000+ TEUs or more).

Figure 5.1 below shows in map form the current trade routes that are extensively exploited by shipping lines such as MSC, CMA-CGM and UAFL.

Figure: 5.1

The volume of trade within the region in financial terms is set out in the table and charts below.

Trade statistics intra-IOC 2012 (Millions €)

Countries	Comoros	Madagascar	Mauritius	Seychelles	La Réunion	Total (€)
Comoros	-	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.5
Madagascar	2.9	-	1.0	2.7	30.6	37.2
Mauritius	1.7	80.5	-	16.1	43.6	141.9
Seychelles	0.0	0.4	1.7	-	2.0	4.1
La Réunion	0.1	16.0	2.2	2.0	-	20.3
Total (€)	4.7	97.1	4.9	20.8	76.5	204.0

Source : Indian Ocean Commission & MCCI

The trade transaction among the IOC member countries during the year 2012 amounted to €204 M.

Out of which, export amounting to €142M (70%) originated from Mauritius and €5m (2%) was imported into Mauritius.

The above chart represents the yearly Export from Reunion Island to IOC member countries. The FOB values expressed in million €.

It is to be noted that exports from Reunion Island to the Seychelles in the years 2011 and 2012 are negligible.

Source: Customs Dept

The above chart represents the yearly Import to Reunion Island from IOC member countries. The CIF values expressed in million €.

Note that import from Comoros to Reunion Island during the year 2012 is negligible.

Source: Customs Dept- Madagascar

Source: Customs Dept- Madagascar

The above charts represent Madagascar Imports and exports trade statistics (Intra-IOC) for the period 2008 to 2012.

Source: Mauritius Customs Department

Source: Mauritius Customs Department

The Chart and tables below present production of the 20 most important food and agricultural commodities ranked by value and quantity in Madagascar for the year 2011

Source: FAOSTAT 2011

Rank	Commodity	Production (Int \$1000)	Production (MT)
1	Rice, paddy	945266	4300185
2	Meat indigenous, cattle	447753	165750
3	Cassava	364607	3490300
4	Mangoes, mangosteens, guavas	180094	300574
5	Milk, whole fresh cow	174754	560000
6	Bananas	98571	350000
7	Sugar cane	96147	3050000
8	Fruit, tropical fresh nes	95427	233504
9	Meat indigenous, pig	85203	55426
10	Cashew apple	70111	74296
11	Vegetables, fresh nes	66783	354397
12	Coffee, green	56740	52813
13	Maize	56600	428390
14	Meat indigenous, chicken	51264	35990
15	Beans, dry	50096	89000
16	Vanilla	49804	3000
17	Sweet potatoes	49627	1102950
18	Taro (cocoyam)	33387	224888
19	Potatoes	26584	209000
20	Meat indigenous, goat	23398	9765

Source: FAOSTAT 2011 – sort by value

Rank	Commodity	Production (Int \$1000)	Production (MT)
1	Rice, paddy	945266	4300185
2	Cassava	364607	3490300
3	Sugar cane	96147	3050000
4	Sweet potatoes	49627	1102950
5	Milk, whole fresh cow	174754	560000
6	Maize	56600	428390
7	Vegetables, fresh nes	66783	354397
8	Bananas	98571	350000
9	Mangoes, mangosteens, guavas	180094	300574
10	Fruit, tropical fresh nes	95427	233504
11	Taro (cocoyam)	33387	224888
12	Potatoes	26584	209000
13	Meat indigenous, cattle	447753	165750
14	Beans, dry	50096	89000
15	Oranges	16698	86403
16	Pineapples	22783	79929
17	Coconuts	8404	76000
18	Cashewapple	70111	74296
19	Meat indigenous, pig	85203	55426
20	Coffee, green	56740	52813

Source: FAOSTAT 2011 – sort by quantity

4.1 Comoros port development

The port

As an island nation, Comoros receives most of its imported goods through its ports. Moroni (located in Grande Comoros) and Mutsamudu (located in Anjouan) are the active ports. Moroni is the main port for the Comoros with an estimated 80% of the country's business volumes. Ports infrastructure is detailed below.

Port	Main quay	Main draught	Main Pier	Main Sheds	Capacity ¹
	Metres	Metres	metres	Metres ²	TEUs
Moroni	100	5	240	2,500	1,700
Mutsamudu	173	9	...	3,000	1,400
Mohéli	70	2

Source: The Hydratec Bureau for the Government of the Union of Comoros and the European Commission, Ernst & Young research

Moroni Port

Mutsamudu port with its deeper draught became prominent since 2005, when the government of Anjouan signed an agreement with Maersk Sealand, one of the world's largest shipping companies. Under this agreement, Mutsamudu acts as a redistribution centre for the other ports such as Moroni, Mozambique, Madagascar, Mayotte, Mauritius, Réunion, Seychelles and Zanzibar. Consequently many cargoes are transhipped at Mutsamudu where larger vessels with draught up to 9 metres can berth.

¹ TEU is a measure of container capacity of Twenty-foot Equivalent Units, where one TEU is the space for one container of twenty feet long, 8ft wide, and 8ft 6 inches high with a cubic capacity of 1,360 cu feet.

Mutsamudu Port - Comoros

Development of a national port Master Plan for the ports of the Comoros islands, 2013 – 2014

Maritime Transport Business Solutions B.V of the Netherlands has been assigned by the CAON (Support Unit to the EDF National Authorising Officer, Comoros) to develop a national port Project for the ports on the Comoros islands. The study provides an integral national Project for Moroni, Matsumudu and Faboni from a commercial, technical, operational, financial, legal and institutional perspective. The studies include analyses on containers, break bulk, transshipment potential, oil, passengers, tourism and fishery industry. The assignment comprises traffic forecasts, investment analyses, Public Private Partnership structuring, financial modeling, operational analysis, safety and security and analyses concerning the potential for new traffic, including transshipment. The port Project would be ready by 2014.

4.2 Madagascar ports' development

The satellite map of the sea ports of Madagascar

Source: World Port Source

Port icons are color coded by size.

Madagascar International Container Terminal at Toamasina, run by Philippines-based International Container Terminal Services (ICTSI) through a 20-year concession signed in 2005, is also planning transshipment activities. Madagascar International Container Terminal Services (MICTS) has stated its ambitions to be "Africa's secondary hub".

In June 2007, ICTSI completed the first phase of its modernisation programme at the terminal. This included a mobile twin lift container crane and four rubber tyred gantries. Other investments included a yard refurbishment (to support the use of the gantries), rehabilitation of the two berths under MICTS control and an implementation of Navis' "SPARCS" terminal automation software system. These investments have led to the terminal becoming one of the most efficient and secure in Africa and will boost the terminal's productivity. Future plans include land expansion, new equipment and upgrades in IT systems in pace with growth in volume of traffic. The terminal currently handles a small amount of transshipment. Opportunities to use the port as a transshipment hub or "jumping off" point for India or Africa are being explored.

PORT OF TOAMASINA

TOAMASINA PORT CONTAINER TERMINAL

The facilities available in these ports are:

Port	Main Quay	Main Draught	Types of traffic
	metres	metres	
Toamasina	365	8	General Cargo
Mahanjanga	51	2	Passenger

	Port of Mahajanga (Majunga),	Port of Mananjary	Port of Morondava
Port details			
Anchorage depth:	6.4m - 7.6m	14m - 15.2m	7.1- 9.1m
Cargo pier depth:	7.1m - 9.1m	1.8m - 3m	1.8 -3m
Oil terminal depth:	9.4m - 10m	N/A	N/A
Harbour size:	Very Small	Very Small	Very Small
Max size:	Over 500 feet in length	N/A	N/A
Shelter:	Fair	Fair	Poor

Antsiranana Harbour (named Diego Suarez Port prior to 1975)

Port of Antsiranana, Madagascar		
Port Details		Port Facilities
Anchorage depth:	7.1m - 9.1m	General container bulk
Cargo pier depth:	7.1m - 9.1m	Towage
Oil terminal depth:	7.1m - 9.1m	Petroleum
Dry dock:	Medium	
Harbour size:	Small	
Max size:	Over 500 feet in length	
Repairs:	Moderate	
Shelter:	Good	

The new Port of Ehoala at the remote south-eastern tip of Madagascar situated in the western Indian Ocean is a multi-use, deep water port constructed for export of ilmenite mineral sands as well as import/export of other cargo to stimulate broader economic development in the region.

The port management is private and entrusted to Port Ehoala SA, a subsidiary of Rio Tinto. The port is open to the public and national and international shipping (Customs Office) utility. It should contribute to the opening of southern Madagascar which is difficult to access by land.

Madagascar is rich in natural resources such as the mineral Sand, ilmenite (titanium dioxide), which is used as a pigment in the production of Paints, Coatings and Plastics. International mining group Rio Tinto Plc. is now mining ilmenite deposits located near the town of Fort Dauphin (Tôlanaro) in the south eastern part of the country for export to processing facilities in North America.

The new Port of Ehoala

The port provides for ilmenite export in Panamax bulk carriers up to 60,000 deadweight tonnes (DWT) as well as fuel import and export in coastal tankers and general cargo and container traffic. Cargo operations include the import of mine supplies and the import and export of container and break bulk cargoes. Excess capacity at the new berth will also be used to attract growth in container services and break bulk cargo.

The port also features comprehensive aids to navigation system designed to International Association of Lighthouse Authorities standards.

4.3 Mauritius port development

Port Louis Harbour is strategically located between Africa, Europe and Asia. It continues to play a leading role in the Mauritian economy by handling 99% of the country's external trade and acting as an engine for growth in the process. Over the past two decades, the port has had substantial investment in modern infrastructure and container facilities, supporting seafood exports, freeport services, logistics, transshipments, cruise ship tourism, with a commercial waterfront development.

The Mauritius Port's Authority, owns most of the port facilities including the superstructure, the terminals, transit sheds and container parks. The port's facilities at Port Louis comprise eleven quays with three terminals, dredged up to 14 metres in depth. The Mauritius Port's Authority has launched two phase port infrastructure development program at Port Louis to be completed by 2016.

PHASE 1

Development works under this phase which started in July 2013 will be completed in 2016. The works entail:-

- Quay extension by 240 m at the Mauritius Container Terminal(MCT)
- Container terminal expansion by 6.5 Ha
- Dredging works to a depth of 16 m to accommodate large container vessels of 8000+ TEUs capacity

The above works will enable the port to accommodate two big container vessels concurrently and increase the capacity of the terminal from 550,000 TEUs to 750,000 TEUs by the same token.

PHASE 2 consists of:

- The quay extension at the MCT by a further 200m
- Increase in capacity of the terminal to 900,000 TEUs

At the end of phase 2, the port with a 1 km long quay will be able to accommodate 3 large container vessels simultaneously.

Further planned port infrastructure development program for the period 2016 to 2020 will include:

- The construction of 2 Km long breakwater
- Land reclaim/Expansion of 60 Ha
- Container park of 40 Ha
- Construction of container terminal
- Increase in capacity of the terminal to I million + TEUs
- Dredging works to accommodate large container vessels of 11000+ TEUs capacity with draft of 18 m

Port Louis Harbour handles around 1.1 million MT of petroleum products annually. With the increased alongside depth of 14.5 m, berthing of bigger tankers of up to 50,000 DWT is now possible. The Oil Jetty, having a throughput capacity of about 4 Million tonnes per annum, is equipped with 8 Pipelines.

As an emerging cruise hub, Port Louis Harbour welcomed 23 cruise vessels in 2012. The total cargo traffic has expanded significantly and has crossed the threshold of 7 million tonnes. The total Container Traffic registered a double digit growth of 19.1%, equivalent to 66,843 TEUs

from 350,624 TEUs in 2011 to attain a new peak of 417,467 TEUs in 2012. This strong performance was bolstered by 37% growth in transshipment activities.

With further expansion phases running through to 2020 together with the on-going development it is envisaged that, the capacity of Port Louis harbour will further improve significantly.

The Government of Mauritius has decided in its 2014 budget to make provision for incentives for promoting exports in Africa. In this context, the Mauritius Government proposes two major measures as follows:

1. provide a subsidy of 25 per-cent of the freight cost on containers exported to all countries in Africa except South Africa and Madagascar. This will be up to a maximum of US 300 dollars per container.
2. provide a 50 per-cent subsidy on the cost of Credit Guarantee Insurance for exports to Africa. Export Credit Guarantee Insurance is essential to cover additional risks when exporting to unfamiliar markets as very often, the premium can be exceedingly high.

Terminal 3 – Mauritius Container Terminal

4.4 La Reunion port development

Le Port

Le Port is the main access point of Réunion for goods. It has two ports, separated by about 3 km. Port West specialises in dry bulk traffic (cereals, sugar, cement), deep sea fishing and the Navy. The terminals of Port East are mainly dedicated to the handling of containers and hydrocarbons. In 2008 the port handled some 4.2 million tonnes

West Port

The northern basin is composed of a sugar terminal, a fishing dock and the dock Fourque reserved for the navy. The south basin is composed of berths for gas, bulk cement and bitumen in bulk, a dedicated berth for oil to the Electricité de France (EDF, one of the world's leading electric utilities) and the small ship and station for cereals. The channel at Port West is dredged to 10m and a width of 70m. It can accommodate ships of 175m in length, a width of 24m and 8.5m in draught. (Table 1)

Port Facilities – West Port

Berth No	Quay Length Metres	Main draught metres	Operation
1	160	8,0	Multipurpose
2	210	10,0	Multipurpose- molasses, bags, diverse special goods
7	210	8,5	Sugar
8	190	8,5	Multipurpose- cruise ships, bunkers, scrap
TS	120	8,5	Fishing industry, bunkers
9	190	8,5	Bulk grain, bunkers
H		7,8	Bitumen, Bulk, Cement & gas

East Port

The East Port is shared between the container activities, the bulk docks and other port activities. The entrance channel and the Ports turning circle are respectively 160m wide and 480m in diameter with a depth of 16m. The docks have a draft of 12.80m and can accommodate vessels of 215m in length and 12m draft. (Table 2)

Port Facilities – East Port

Berth No	Quay Length Metres	Main draught Metres	Operations
10	255	12	Containers, hydrocarbons
11	255	12	Containers
14	255	12	Multipurpose- general cargo, ro- ro, containers
15	255	12	Multipurpose- Cruise ships, Solid bulk, general cargo, containers

Source: Ports Association of Indian Ocean Islands

The island has a modern and efficient infrastructure of European level. The container terminal is equipped with four panamax gantry cranes with an estimated capacity of 300,000 TEU. (Table3) Operations are managed by 3 companies (SGM, SOMACOM, MRSA) that are coordinated within a GIE. They also handle the maintenance activities.

Réunion Port Statistics, Containers; TEUs 2004 to 2008

	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	CAGR 2004-2008
Import/Export	179,038	185,914	197,561	218,376	234,866	7.02%
Transshipment	13,970	3,233	3276	6297	20,505	10.07%
Total	193,008	189,147	200,837	224,673	255,371	7.25%

Source: ICF GHK based on Agence Française de Développement

The storage covers an area of 45 hectares including 1.4 hectares of refrigerated warehouses in compliance with European standards and regulations (hygiene, quality, safety and traceability) offering a good point for the distribution of goods across the entire Indian Ocean.

4.5 Seychelles port development

Thanks to the country's industrial fishing industry, Port Victoria has developed to a high level for such a small country. The high level of shipping crossing from South Asia and the Gulf to the east coast of Africa has led to Seychelles being added to the itineraries of a number of major shipping lines; in a show of confidence that Port Victoria can provide the on-shore services they and their clients expect.

However, in early 2013, Maersk Shipping Line has changed their schedules and service patterns to stop using Port Victoria for transshipment traffic. Maersk Shipping Line is currently using Salalah Port for relay transshipment for the Indian Ocean Islands. Shipment to and from Port Victoria is now covered under the Maersk Indian Ocean Islands weekly service. CMA-CGM shipping line also has a weekly service call to Port Victoria operating from Djibouti Port.

The potential for Port Victoria harbour could be greatly developed through investment in equipment and deeper draft. In this respect, the Government has an ambitious two hundred million US dollar project to maintain Port Victoria's position as the region's pre-eminent fisheries hub and fuel bunkering point, as well as to enable it to realise its potential as a container transshipment point serving the western Indian Ocean and east African seaboard. The plan envisages a major expansion of the ports existing facilities, covering much of the reclaimed land surrounding the existing fisheries and cargo quays. A new road network, fuel farm, dry dock and free trade area will be constructed to support the major planned expansion of the ports fisheries quay which will grow by more than 300 meters and cargo quays which will also be provided with an additional 50,000 m for container movements. The project will be completed in phases and will start with the construction of two dolphin quays to facilitate the loading and unloading of nets for repairs and salt for use by the purse seiners.

Further investment opportunities will be created through the relocation and expansion of the Inter-island quay, which provides services to travellers between Mahé and other islands in the archipelago. The present quay will be converted into a long line fishing port for both local and foreign-owned vessels.

Port Victoria

Port	Main quay	Main draught	Operations
	metres	metres	
Mahé, Victoria: Commercial	370	11.6	Container, cargo, bunkering, passenger, warships, warehousing, cargo stevedore.
Mahé, Victoria: Industrial fishing	36	7.5	Fisheries unloading and transportation, bunkering,
Mahé, Victoria: inter island	130	5	Passengers, cargo
Other smaller islands	Jetties for passengers and cargo

Port Victoria is equipped with modern cargo handling equipment including mobile cranes, front-end handlers and reach stackers, container handling forklifts, specialized terminal tractors and trailers, and self-loading container trucks. The terminal has a total area of 9,600 square meters and covered storage space of 6,600 square meters. With an extensive space for container handling, it handles almost all of the nation's external trade and plays host to many cruise ships. The port is under the management of the Seychelles Port Authority.

5. Economic and Financial Issues

The present maritime operators of the area do not meet the growing needs of the members of the IOC. This is a frustrating issue which is inhibiting the growth of trade. The strategies for development of services of the different current maritime operators do not correspond to those of the Member States of the IOC and the timeframe of their plans for improvements do not meet their needs. Manufacturers and traders depend on international carriers, and have little, or no, ability to negotiate new services or prices. Current inter-state transport represents 30-40% of the cost of consumer products without the possibility of intervention of the States and even less the consumers.

The carriers working within the region blame costly delays on inadequate infrastructure, lack of links with national transport facilities with poor roads, no railways, and poor management of the complex logistics, together with maintenance difficulties of existing infrastructure and of the incompatibility of the systems of transport between them. The result is that, in most countries of the IOC, the cost of transport is high, lacks flexibility and is not competitive in the global market. To overcome these issues it is necessary to modernize the transport infrastructure, and establish a region-wide maritime system more geared towards the growing needs of the countries with the aim of facilitating improvements in the volume and better targeting of the distribution of goods and services.

The region has several sea ports which have undertaken to upgrade their operations and services as well as their infrastructure use and management. This process focuses primarily on improving the operational links with the private sector through the outsourcing of operations and services, in particular the handling of containers. But the pace of reforms must be accelerated to allow customers to remove their goods faster and get more competitive services.

The costs of these reforms will be high and beyond the financial capacity of some countries. The European Union (EU) launched in July 2006, an EU-Africa Infrastructure Partnership Program designed to support Africa's efforts to identify the weak links in existing networks and tackle it, but also to harmonize the transport policies in accordance with the AU/NEPAD priorities.

The World Bank expects that by 2025, fast growing developing economies and transition economies led by China, India, Brazil, Russian Federation, Indonesia and Republic of Korea will account for more than 50% of global growth. The share of all developing countries in international trade flows has also increased significantly rising from 36.2% in 1995 to an estimated 42% in 2010*. Such developments will increase the demand for global transport for the wider pattern and greater volume of trade. Detailed financial and economic evaluations are needed and must be based upon the identification of the principal direct and indirect economic benefits associated with the Project and the expected capital and operating costs.

The principal benefits associated with the Project are as follows:

- Accommodation for larger ships (8000+ TEU) at the regional transshipment port with appropriate/additional quay cranes,
- Additional revenues associated with the increased number of ship calls (Feeder vessels & Mother ships),
- Additional revenues associated with the increased transshipment activities at container terminals,

- Unit Cost savings (on fuel and human resources) due to economy of scale derived from the use of larger ships.

It is assumed that there will be sufficient competition between the service line providers operating in the region to ensure that the cost savings arising from the deployment of larger ships are passed on to the importers and exporters of the region in the form of lower freight rates.

The Project is expected to have a positive long term effect on the foreign exchange and will provide potential for countries of the region to diversify their economies, increase their export base, develop their infrastructures, and increase their underexploited intra-regional trade.

In the short run, however, there may be an outflow of foreign exchange for capital expenditure mostly geared towards port and related transport infrastructure development, the negative effect of which would be outweighed by the long run direct and indirect economic benefits. The Project will bring more vessels to the region. In addition there will be more employment arising from support activities in the port such as bunkering, shipchandling and repairs.

There will also be substantial indirect impact of these developments through demand for other goods and services and activities of related industries and consumer services with a multiplier impact.

The direct employment effect of the Project can be estimated in relation to the increased volume and frequency of shipping but the wider economic impact is less easy to evaluate. Further review and assessment is needed.

The Maritime Project will produce risks of some negative externalities through increased traffic and the threat of oil pollution, disturbance of fishing grounds, maritime stocks and disposal of toxic waste at sea in a sensitive ecological region. This will require careful assessment and the provision of adaptation, mitigation and contingency plans in the face of the risks environmental stress, and of maritime disasters and accidents. The risks of disruption of services in the cyclone season will need to be assessed.

The setting up of a regional maritime system in the Indian Ocean region will require legal and licensing provisions, which are closely related to the external policy followed by the different countries and the different bilateral and multilateral agreements entered into with other countries in the region including World Trade Organization.

Estimates have been made of the income and operating costs of the Project. These are based on the planned level of trade activities, the expected container handling fees, port charges applicable at the relevant ports and the operating cost associated with the types of vessels to be deployed. The financial evaluation looks at changes in cash flows to the new shipping company arising from the Project.

Future prospects in maritime transport development seem to be optimistic. COSCO, the largest Chinese maritime operator expressed interest in the IOC project and in 2013 several meetings were held with the IOC. On the 26th of June 2013, a high level delegation of COSCO met with IOC Permanent Liaison Officer and representatives of the General Secretariat. Subsequent exchanges were held between the IOC Secretary General and the Group Management at the COSCO's headquarters in November 2013 during an official visit to China.

Yearly Financial estimates– 2 Regional Transshipment Ports + 1 Feeder line as recommended by Maritime Logistics and Trade

The yearly financial estimates are based upon the existing level of activities at respective transshipment ports are as follows:

Yearly Financial Forecast Line	Transshipment Port 1	Transshipment Port 2	Feeder	Vessels
(EURO) €	€	€	€	€
Actual Laden Capacity Rate	61%	80%		89%
Income	25,631,800	36,608,650		17,016,400
Less				
Container Handling Charges	17,058,690	22,684,685		10,208,329
Fixed Cost-Port Fees	6,759,957	7,722,795		2,508,661
Vessel Operating Cost	11,782,800	11,782,800		4,776,681
Net Surplus/ (Deficit)	(9,359,647)	(5,151,630)		(477,271)
From operations				
Total Deficit:	(EURO)	€ (14,988,548)		

As highlighted in Chapter 5, the study undertaken in 2009 by Maritime Logistics and Trade Consulting did not take into consideration the potential of other linkages such as East Africa and the Indian Ocean region, West and East Coast of Madagascar through ports Tuléar, Majunga, Diego Suarez, F. Dauphin, Nosy-Bé and Eloha. The regular feeder services between Mombasa and Dar-re-Salaam, Durban, Mogadishu, Djibouti, Salalah and Dubai have also not been considered. Nor did it assess the wider economic benefits of the increased trade.

The port of Mombasa, Kenya acts as a gateway for export to the African countries mainly Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda and other landlocked countries of the region. Although export to the African region is the main focus for exporters of the IOC member countries, the issue of connectivity remains a huge obstacle to the development of this export market. Indeed, the lead time and high freight costs do not allow exporters from the IOC member countries to be competitive.

The potential linkages involving West Africa and the Eastern Coast of South America need also to be considered in conjunction with the changes in the main shipping line with the introduction of larger vessels 9000 to 12000 + TEUs on the East and West main shipping routes. For the proposed new shipping company to operate at full capacity, it will entail an increase of 65% in the trade volume on the Europe Route, with transshipment at Port Reunion, 24% increase in trade volume on the Far East route with transshipment at Port Louis and 11% on the feeder vessel line. The financial evaluation looks at the monetary costs and revenues accruing to the proposed regional company

Yearly consolidated Financial Forecast (Transshipment at 2 Regional Ports) + Feeder Vessel Line	
€	
(EURO)	
Forecast Laden Capacity Rate	100%
Income	106,694,971
Less	
Container Handling Charge	61,503,439
Fixed Cost- Port Fees	7,876,972
Vessel Operating Cost	27,122,281
Container Costs	3,731,000
Agency Commission	2,667,374
Other cost	12,269,922
Net Surplus/ (Deficit)	(EURO) € (8,476,017)
From operations	

Operating at full capacity with two regional transshipment ports together with one feeder vessel line will reduce the deficit from € -14.98M to € -8.47M

The report defined three steps in making progress in establishing a viable shipping company without the need for government subsidy:

- (1) Review of market demand,
- (2) Tariff negotiations,
- (3) Review of operating costs.

Various fixed operating costs are included in the financial forecast. The port fixed costs applicable (inclusive of pilot fees, anchorage, tug service etc) for the two types of vessels namely Pearl Rivier and Birk at different ports within the region are as follows:

Vessel Type	<u>Pearl River</u>	<u>Birk</u>
Port Fixed Costs (Vessel)	<u>Amount</u>	<u>Amount</u>
Port Louis	USD 2,994	USD 2,994
Port Réunion	USD 11,979	USD 8,878
Longoni	USD 17,776	-
Toamasina	USD 5,373	-
Victoria	-	USD 839
Moroni	-	USD 3,054

From the above it can be observed that the fixed costs applicable at the regional ports vary from USD 839 to USD 17,776.

The Indian Ocean Feeder Service shall use small geared ships of 600-900 TEU, which are unlikely to increase very much in size because of restrictions at the other ports in the region. The ability to accommodate larger ships (8000 TEU or more) at the identified transshipment ports with additional quays and cranes require huge investments. Moreover the operating cost

per day for such a type of vessel is about USD 35,000. Increased port efficiency (in terms of berth occupancy rate) will play a very important role in the selection of regional transshipment ports by shipping lines.

It is recommended to have one regional transshipment port that will also be able to handle larger ships (8000 TEUs or more). The final choice of the transshipment port should be left to the private operators.

On 21 October 2013 at the 9th Indian Ocean Economic Forum held in Mauritius the issue of having one regional transshipment port was discussed. Delegates from Comoros, Madagascar, Reunion, Seychelles, Mayotte, Rodrigues and Mauritius attended the Economic Forum.

The introduction of larger ships of 11000+ TEUs capacity on the East to west routes will lead to the shifting of smaller ships of 7000-9000 TEUs to lower density routes such as Asia to Africa routes. In fact there are benefits to be derived from the operation of such large ships. For example:

- The additional revenues associated with the increased in the number of ship calls (Feeder vessels & Large Mother ships)
- The additional revenues associated with the increased in transshipment activities at container terminals.
- Cost savings (on fuel) due to economy of scale derived from the use of larger ships;
- Increased employment and entrepreneurial opportunities for burgeoning younger population.

The costs savings arising from the use of larger ships could be passed on to the importers and exporters of the region in the form of lower freight rates. This in turn will contribute to the improvement of connectivity of regional markets, facilitating trade, transport of passengers and promoting inclusive and equitable development. The increase in trade volume will make the freight rates more competitive.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

There are sufficient economic and financial indications in this report supporting the setting up of a Regional Maritime Service to harness the potential for development.

There is clear indication of large potential for trade and economic development in the Eastern and Southern African region demonstrating high growth rates. The Tripartite region constitutes a market and an opportunity to further explore. The Program for Infrastructure Development in Africa (PIDA) has expected that sub-Saharan Africa will have an average annual economic growth rate of more than 6 % for the next 30 years. The IOC region should strive to make the link between the Asian emerging economies and Africa.

The Project objectives are important to the economic integration of the region and its participation in the global economy. The Island States, characterized by their insularity, isolation and narrowness of markets, with non-diversified economies, far from the markets they serve, are particularly vulnerable to adverse potential negative effects of globalization. It is clear that the priorities for these countries are: to diversify their economies, increase their export base, develop their infrastructures, and increase their underexploited maritime trade. In short, to promote growth focussed on inclusive development. Several sectors, the main one being the agricultural sector provides opportunities for increased growth. However the lack of a Regional Maritime Service acts as a major constraint.

This report is presented to promote further support for the project, to stimulate further development of the national plans and to seek interest in commitment and investment in a Regional Maritime Service.

It is in the above context that the IOC's role is defined.

The following recommendations are made:

1. The IOC should continue to contribute to the improvement of connectivity of regional markets, facilitating trade, the movement of people, and the promotion of inclusive and equitable growth.
2. Given the potential for deepening and enlarging the markets and the linkage to be developed between the Asian emerging markets and Africa, an IOC Regional Export to Africa Strategy needs to be formulated.
3. The IOC should facilitate the development of the Regional Maritime Service to set up a viable and sustainable regional maritime system with modern infrastructure, services, a regional shipping line and agreements on cabotage.
4. There is sufficient willingness on the part of the Member States for the project. However, a more active role of the Member States is to be demonstrated. Detailed study and assessment of the development costs, the expected operating costs and the wider economic and social benefits is necessary to allow the Project to be further developed and consolidated. Further planning is required to assess the detailed development costs, to specify more clearly the logistics of proposed shipping movements and to evaluate the overall economic returns. The three Member States; Comoros, Mauritius and Seychelles which are already committed to the project should not lose time; but meet and discuss actions forward. The General Secretariat will call for the 2nd meeting of the RMC early next year. This can constitute an opportunity to consult on the way forward and agree on how to get the Member States take the lead

in this project, given that the role of the IOC is restricted to one of facilitation and coordination.

5. The government of Mauritius has shown the way to stimulate and accelerate the process. In order to stimulate trade, the government of Mauritius will, during 2014, support Mauritian enterprises in their efforts to expand their exports into African markets. A subsidy of 25% of the freight cost on containers exported to all countries in Africa except South Africa and Madagascar with a maximum of US 300 dollars per container has been earmarked. A 50% subsidy on the cost of Credit Guarantee Insurance for exports to Africa will also be provided in order to cover additional risks when exporting to unfamiliar markets. Such a regional mechanism should be studied and explored in the context of the development of the Project on the Regional Maritime Service.
6. Discussions should continue with COSCO to further engage it in the project. Other companies in the region or elsewhere interested in this venture should be encouraged as well.
7. There is a need to strengthen cooperation in the Indianoceanie so as to significantly improve data and information on trade in the region. This initiative will be closely associated to the Regional Maritime Service Project, as it can allow decision makers to assess the maritime service, while providing tools to measure the services' efficiency. The IOC will promote and reinforce cooperation between customs and concerned departments on economic and trade data. A first list of strategic commodities for the development of the IOC region can be prepared with the aim to:
 - Having a deeper understanding of trends on trade for the IOC member States;
 - Helping decision making towards development of intra-regional trade;
 - Enabling efficient monitoring of these decisions.
8. The development of the Regional Maritime Service should proceed in parallel with the formulation of the Regional Food Security Programme. The success of one Programme depends on the achievement of the other.

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